

‘A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE STATUS OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF URBAN AREA UP BOARD AND CBSE BOARD SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS’

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Abstract:

Educational outcomes always have its importance in the social as well as occupational life of an individual. Without having good knowledge of the subjects in the academic fields no one considered as the good student. Therefore it is very important to secure good marks or performance in the form of grades for better opportunities in the upcoming future tasks. Present problem considers the comparative study of the academic achievement of senior secondary school students. The investigator selected the sample from the senior secondary schools located in urban areas of Bareilly division. Descriptive survey method was employed for analysis of the sample. With the help of mean, standard deviation and t- ratio the data was analyzed. The results showed that there is no significant difference was found between the academic achievement of male, female and total students when the UP and CBSE board schools were taken as the comparative groups. The study also explored that the mean scores of CBSE board female and total students was better than the UP board female and total students. On the other hand mean academic achievement score of male students of UP board schools was better than the mean scores of CBSE board male students.

Key words: *Rural, urban, Girls, Students, Education, Literacy, Muslims, Women.*

Academic achievement is considered as the major aspect of students’ capacity and skills in the sense of knowledge, skills and working efficiency. This is the not the new thing in Indian society. Academic achievement is thought to be the overall personality reflection of an individual. A less or very low academic percentage is of no value itself. Degrees without any distinction or high academic percentages have no value in the sense of getting better placements.

Kohli (1977) pointed that without considering achievement, a degree gives a very little. For the better occupational possibilities, one has to focus on its scholastic performance throughout his educational period. Achievement in school subjects also works as the norms and assurance of one’s career aspiration and his strength (Lent *et al.* 2000).

Academic achievement is generally implies as the marks obtained by the students in his academic year or in the final examination generally conducted in the last of the session. While in some courses the formative and summative examination system are being considered in which sum of the formative and summative exams form the total marks of the students in the end of the session. Goods (1973) defined the academic achievement as “*the academic achievement seems to be similar in the sense of knowledge attainment or skill development to the scores of a test.*” Gupta (1973) categorized the factors which affect the academic achievement into three categories-Capabilities, Efforts and Environmental conditions. Many other elements as mental abilities, specific qualities, personal interests, aptitude, medium of instruction, language, assessment techniques, and socio-economic status may also play the significant role in success the examinations.

Crow & Crow (1969) also analyzed it as the mastery over content instructed in some area in an institution. Thus in the general sense academic achievement can be taken as the knowledge or proficiency in the given area or subjects as to be in the consideration.

Sood, V. (2012) analyzed the need of achievement (n-achievement) among high school adolescents with respect to academic achievement and some demographic variances. The study revealed that achievement of secondary school learners was significantly influenced by n achievement while no significant change found in academic achievement and n achievement among rural-urban and nuclear-joint families.

Raju, S.R. & Reddy, B.R. (2012) also tested the relationship between student's personality aspects (gender, community, caste, area, economic status) and achievement performance in physical sciences. Analysis of the study showed that gender and caste of learners had significant impact over the academic achievement of learners in physical sciences while community, area and economic status had no effect.

Borges *et al.* (2012) investigated and pointed many factors which effect academic performance of school going teens. Outcomes of the study showed that adjustment and learning strategies do not affect the academic achievement as much as the intelligence, motivation and study habits do.

Chaudhary, P. (2010) tried to study the scholastic performance of tribal pupils of Ashram schools of Surat district. Outcomes of the study showed that tribal students were found average in languages like Gujarati, Hindi and below average in English. They are average in Social Science and Math while below average in Science and Technology.

Rationale of the study:

Academic achievement is no doubt a relevant and always the basic criteria for the students. On the basis of achievement level many of the things changes and varies accordingly. In all the fields of education and social development achievement and performance norms strictly followed. Especially in the field of academics, many of the schemes and courses selection criterion are based on the level of the mastery on the respective dimension. That's why it is very needful for the students as well as the teachers to observe it systematically. The present problem tries to check the academic achievement status and differences between them if exists in urban area senior secondary schools affiliated to UP board and CBSE board. This may be very fruitful to know the reasons of the differences in the academic achievement if exists in the region and further steps to remove the dissimilarities.

Statement of Problem:

“A study of the status of academic achievement of rural and urban area senior secondary schools”

Objectives of the study:

1. To study the academic achievement of UP board students in the urban area senior secondary schools.
2. To study the academic achievement of CBSE board students in the urban area senior secondary schools.
3. To study the difference in academic achievement of UP board and CBSE board students in the urban area senior secondary schools.

Hypothesis of the study:

1. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area male students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools
2. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area female students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools
3. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools

Delimitation of the study:

The study is delimited to only 280 urban area senior secondary school students of UP and CBSE board in Bareilly division. Only government, aided and private senior secondary school students are taken in the study.

Methodology:

The researcher employed descriptive survey method to describe the status of the problem. For this to be accomplished, the investigator selected 280 pupils randomly from different senior secondary schools of UP and CBSE board from the Bareilly division. Bareilly division covers four district including Bareilly, Pilibhit, Budaun and Shahjahanpur. The data was collected in the form of percentage of marks gained by the students in the XI class annual examinations. The data is then analyzed with the help of SPSS software to calculate the required statistics.

Analysis and Results:

H01. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area male students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools.

Table 1 shows the t-test statistics of academic achievement of urban area male students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools

Board	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Level of significance	Remark at 0.05 level
UP Board	70	57.47	7.30	0.379	0.05	Not Significant
CBSE Board	70	56.90	10.34			

From table 1, it is clear that the mean academic achievement score of male students of UP board and CBSE board urban senior secondary schools are 57.47 and 56.90 respectively. Their standard deviations are 7.30 and 10.34 respectively. It is clear from the table that the calculated value of t (0.379) is not significant at 0.05 level of significance and 138 degrees of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area male students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools is accepted. It is also reflects from the table 1 that the mean value of academic achievement of UP Board male students of urban senior secondary schools is somewhat better than the mean value of their counterparts of CBSE board. This may be some liberal marking by the teachers in the home exams or tendency to show the better outcomes in the UP board schools attract the stakeholders for the UP board schools.

H02. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area female students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools.

Table 2 shows the t-test statistics of academic achievement of urban area female students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools.

Board	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Level of significance	Remark at 0.05 level
UP Board	70	59.40	9.44	1.60	0.05	Not Significant
CBSE Board	70	62.12	10.56			

From table 2, it is clear that the mean academic achievement score of female students of UP board and CBSE board urban senior secondary schools are 59.40 and 62.12 respectively. Their standard deviations are 9.44 and 10.56 respectively. It is clear from the table that the calculated value of t (1.60) is not significant at 0.05 level of significance and 138 degrees of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area female students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools is accepted. It is also reflects from the table 2 that the mean value of academic achievement of CBSE Board female students of urban senior secondary schools is somewhat better than the mean value of their counterparts of UP board. This may be some motivational strategies employed by the CBSE board teachers as compare to the UP board ones.

H03. There is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools

Table 3 shows the t -test statistics of academic achievement of urban area students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools.

Board	N	Mean	S.D.	't' value	Level of significance	Remark at 0.05 level
UP Board	70	58.44	8.46	0.928	0.05	Not Significant
CBSE Board	70	59.51	10.74			

From table 3, it is clear that the mean academic achievement score of students of UP board and CBSE board urban senior secondary schools are 58.44 and 59.51 respectively. Their standard deviations are 8.46 and 10.74 respectively. It is clear from the table that the calculated value of t (0.928) is not significant at 0.05 level of significance and 138 degrees of freedom. Therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in academic achievement of urban area students of UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools is accepted. It is also reflects from the table 3 that the mean value of academic achievement of CBSE Board students of urban senior secondary schools is somewhat better than the mean value of their counterparts of UP board. This may possibly due to some better infrastructural facilities and innovative techniques employed by the CBSE board teachers.

Findings of the study:

1. The mean score of academic achievement of UP Board male students of urban senior secondary schools is found greater than the mean score of CBSE board male students of urban senior secondary schools.
2. The mean score of academic achievement of CBSE Board female students of urban senior secondary schools is found greater than the mean score of UP board female students of urban senior secondary schools.
3. The mean score of academic achievement of CBSE Board students of urban senior secondary schools is found greater than the mean score of UP board students of urban senior secondary schools.
4. There is no significant difference existed in academic achievement of male students of urban area UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools.
5. There is no significant difference existed in academic achievement of female students of urban area UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools.
6. There is no significant difference existed in academic achievement of students of urban area UP Board and CBSE board senior secondary schools.

Conclusion:

All the activities conducted in an institution have the primary motive to make the students more capable, skillful and competent in their field. Therefore the overall academic performance is the key indicator for the learning of the students. In this sense academic achievement is very important issue. It is the fact that the urban society schools have better infrastructure services as compare to their counterparts. This is fact why all the aware guardians wish to admit their children in the urban schools for better output and growth of their child. From the outcomes of the study it is observed that senior secondary school students' academic output is better in both the schools of UP board as well as CBSE board and there is negligible difference is found in both type of institutions. Hence it can be concluded that Urban society schools whether it is affiliated to UP board or CBSE board and their academic indicator is much more same which seems to be good socio economic aspect of the students.

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